

Multiple Sequence Alignment and Phylogenetic Tree of Human and Viral Helicases

Introduction

Helicases are a type of enzyme that unwinds the double helix structure of DNA or RNA (Huttner et al., Brenner's Encyclopedia of Genetics, 2013). They play a critical role in many biological processes, including DNA replication, transcription, and repair in humans but also in human pathogens such as viruses (Raney et al., Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology, 2014). Studying these proteins can lead to further insight into their mechanism of action in healthy tissues and a variety of diseases, including cancer, viral infections, and genetic disorders, which may guide the development of new drugs.

Helicase plays a key role in the maintenance of genomic stability, therefore the accumulation of mutations or DNA damage in certain helicases has been linked to the development of cancer (Bochman, Molecular and Cellular Oncology, 2014). For example, mutations in the BRCA1 and BRCA1 helicases have been discovered to contribute to breast, ovarian, and pancreatic cancer (Cantor et al., PNAS, 2004). In addition, helicases play an important role in the replication of many viruses and have been reported to be promising targets in antiviral treatment for herpes simplex virus (HSV), shingles, and hepatitis C viruses (Shadrack et al., Journal of Biomolecular Screening, 2013). For example, Pritelivir, a helicase inhibitor targeting HSV, is currently in its phase III clinical trials and the antiviral drug, Amenamevir, has been approved in Japan for the treatment of shingles (Shadrack et al., Journal of Biomolecular Screening, 2013). Finally, inherited genetic disorders such as Bloom syndrome and Werner syndrome are caused by defects in specific helicases.

The RNA/DNA unwinding activity of helicase is coupled with ATP hydrolysis and, while helicases can have very diverse domain architectures, they all contain a core helicase (also referred to as RecA) ATP-binding domain containing specific motifs that are used to classify them into six sub-families (SF1-SF6) (Webb et al., Encyclopedia of Biophysics, 2013). All the superfamilies possess the Walker A and Walker B motifs (motifs I and II), which are involved in the binding and hydrolysis of ATP. The superfamilies also all possess an arginine finger (R), which assists in coupling the ATP hydrolysis reaction into a conformational change (Fairman-Williams et al., Nucleic acids/Sequences and Topology, 2010). The SF1 and SF2 helicases share twelve out of thirteen motifs (Q, I, Ia, Ib, Ic, II, III, IV, V, Va, Vb, VI), which can fold into RecA-like domains (RecA-like N-terminal domain and Rec-like C-terminal domain; Figure 1,2). The cleft between the two RecA-like domains, formed by the Q, I, II, and VI motifs, is the site where ATP binding occurs. The motifs that are responsible for the coordination between the ATP and nucleic acid binding sites for translocation are motifs III and Va

(Figure 2). These motifs are less conserved between the two families (Figure 1). Finally, motifs Ia, Ib, Ic, IV, V, and Vb are thought to be involved in nucleic acid binding.

Figure 1. The figure shows the sequence conservation within SF1 and SF2 helicase motifs. The level of conservation at each position is reflected by the height of the amino acids (AA). The colours of the amino acids represent its chemical property: green and purple AAs are polar, blue AAs are basic, red AAs are acidic, and black AAs are hydrophobic. Figure is taken from Fairman-Williams et al., *Nucleic acids / Sequences and topology*, 2010.

Figure 2. This figure presents the positions of conserved motifs in each superfamily of helicase. The RecA N-terminal helicase domain is represented as a blue box and the RecA C-terminal helicase domain is shaded in brown. The motifs involved in ATP binding and hydrolysis are shown in yellow and the motifs that contribute to

translocation are coloured green. The motifs which interact with nucleic acids are coloured in blue. The brown ovals highlight motifs that are unique to each helicase superfamily. The AAA+ protein fold in SF6 is represented as blue rectangles. This figure was taken from Jackson et al., *Current Opinion in Structural Biology*, 2014.

Helicases in superfamily 1 are involved in a wide variety of processes in both RNA and DNA metabolism within all organisms (Raney et al., *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, 2013). They can be divided into two sub groups according to the polarity of translocation along the DNA or RNA. SF1A helicases have a translocation directionality of 3'-5' (PcrA, Rep, and UvrD helicases) and SF1B helicases have a directionality of 5'-3' (RecD and Dda helicases; Raney et al., *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, 2013).

Figure 3. Helicase motifs and structure of superfamily 1. (a) Schematic representation of the RecA N-terminal helicase domain (in red) and the RecA C-terminal helicase domain (in dark blue) in the SF1 helicase, PcrA. (b) Crystal structure of PcrA (PDB 3PJR) that is in complex with an ATP analogue (in turquoise) and a DNA substrate (in purple and black). (c) Same as (b) where SF1 helicase motifs are colour-coded (motif I (Walker A): in dark blue; Ia light blue, II (Walker B) red, III green, IV purple, IVa dark green, V yellow, and VI brown). (d) This structure is a space-filling representation model using the same colouring seen in structure (c). This figure was taken from Singleton et al., *Annual Review of Biochemistry*, 2007.

The largest helicase family is superfamily 2, this family is involved in many different cellular processes (Beyer et al., *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*, 2012). Subgroups of SF2 helicases have characteristic accessory domains that direct the activity of their core domains, this contributes to their diverse cellular functions in DNA replication, RNA metabolism, and protein translation (Chamieh et al., *Gene*, 2016). Members in this family have the unique motif, IVa, which is responsible for the interaction with nucleic acids (Fairman-Williams et al., *Nucleic acids/Sequences and Topology*, 2010).

Figure 4. Structure of the SF2 DEAD-box helicase family. (A) Schematic representation of the RecA N-terminal helicase domain (RecA1; in yellow) and the RecA C-terminal helicase domain (RecA2; in green). The motifs characteristic of SF2 helicases are represented as black vertical lines. Walker A and B are represented as I and II, respectively. The crystal structure of melanogaster Vasa protein (PDB 2DB3) bound to an ATP analogue and RNA is shown with the same colour scheme. This figure was adapted from Ozgur et al., *The FEBS Journal*, 2014.

Unlike SF1 and SF2, SF3-6 helicases do not have a C-terminal helicase domain (Figure 2). SF3 helicases only contain four conserved motifs: Walker A and B, B', and C (Figure 2 and 5; Naves, *IdRef*, 2018). The novel C motif is specific to SF3. Members of this family are only encoded by DNA and RNA viruses (Hickman et al., *Current Opinion in Structural Biology*, 2005). SF3 helicases possess a core domain that is similar to AAA+ proteins (ATPase associated with a variety of cellular activities). This core contains the nucleotide-binding motifs in the central beta strands and a set of loops that are involved in DNA binding or protein-protein interactions (Hickman et al., *Current Opinion in Structural Biology*, 2005).

Figure 5. (A) A ribbon representation of SF3-6 helicase. Each helicase monomer is represented with its own colour. The bound nucleotide is represented in space-filling mode in light blue (PDB 2GXA; 1E0J; 1PV4; 1IN4). (B) This figure depicts the conserved helicase motifs of SF3-6 in a single monomer (PDB 2GXA; 1E0J; 1PV4; 1IN4). The monomers in SF3, 4, and 6 are bound to a nucleotide, coloured light blue. This figure was adapted from Singleton et al., Annual Review of Biochemistry, 2007.

Superfamily 4 helicases are mostly replicative helicases that all have type B polarity (5'-3'; Passricha et al., Helicases from All Domains of Life, 2019). They have five conserved motifs: Walker A (H1), H1a, Walker B (H2), H3 and H4 (Figure 2 and 5). The motifs H1a, H3, and H4 are only unique to SF4 helicases (Passricha et al., Helicases from All Domains of Life, 2019).

Superfamily 5 is the smallest family of helicases and possesses a 5'-3' polarity. It is an important member of Rho transcription termination in bacteria. The transcription terminator Rho is related to SF4 but has been classified as a separate family based on its sequence. SF5 has three conserved sequences: Walker A (I), Ia, and Walker B (II; Figure 2 and 5; Passricha et al., Helicases from All Domains of Life, 2019).

Superfamily 6 helicases are hexameric motor proteins containing the AAA+ core that do not fit within the SF3 categorization (Singleton et al., Annual Review of Biochemistry, 2007). This family has four conserved motifs: Walker A (I), Walker B (II), S1, and S2 (Figure 2; Passricha et al., Helicases from All Domains of Life, 2019). The position of the arginine finger (R), S1, and S2 are unique to members of SF6 (Passricha et al., Helicases from All Domains of Life, 2019).

Figure 6. SF1-6 crystal structures in complex with ATP analogues (orange) and nucleic acids (dark green). The N- and C-RecA-like helicase domains in SF1 (PDB 3PJR) and SF2 (PDB 2DB3) are shown in purple and dark blue, respectively. The accessory domains or insertions within all of the superfamilies are coloured in grey. The hexameric and monomeric structures of SF3-5 (PDB 2GXA; 3ICE; 1PV4) helicases are presented side by side. Each monomer within the hexameric helicases of SF3-5 are represented in different colours. Within the monomeric helicase of SF3-6, the helicase core domain is coloured differently (SF4 in pink, SF5 in orange, and SF6 in light green) from the rest of the monomer (grey). There is no hexameric crystal structure for the RuvB SF6 helicase (PDB 1IN4) therefore, only the monomer is shown.

Figure 7. A close up of the NTP (space-filling model; orange) binding pockets in SF1-6 crystal structures. The binding pockets of each superfamily is presented as a semi-transparent mesh model. The N- and C-terminal RecA-like helicase domain is coloured purple and dark blue, respectively, in the SF1 and SF2 crystal structure. The different coloured ribbons in SF3-5 correlate to the helicase core in separate subunits. The grey ribbons within all superfamilies represent the rest of the helicases. SF6 does not have a hexameric crystal structure, therefore the binding pocket consists of only one helicase subunit (green), despite there being evidence to suggest that multiple subunits are involved in NTP binding.

Because the helicase domain is the only domain present in all helicases, it is considered a promising target for drug discovery (Young and Karbstein, *Methods in Enzymology*, 2012). However, the presence of druggable binding pockets in this domain and their structural diversity have not been systematically analyzed.

Constructing multiple sequence alignments is an important process in the study of helicases. They allow researchers to compare the sequence of multiple related protein sequences in order to identify similarities and differences between them. These alignments can provide valuable insights into the function, structure, and evolution of the sequences being compared.

Finally, aligning the sequences of helicases from both humans and viruses may reveal druggable pockets that are conserved, and guide medicinal chemistry strategies.

As a first step, I am describing here my effort in generating a multiple sequence alignment of human helicases, as well as helicases from viruses representing a pandemic threat. I then converted this alignment into a phylogenetic tree of human and viral helicases.

Methods

- All human proteins that contain the Interpro domain [IPR014001](#), [IPR014013](#), [IPR041677](#), [IPR001208](#), [IPR027785](#), and [IPR014017](#) were extracted from [ChemBioPort](#) (Liu et al, Database 2022).
 - [IPR014001](#): **Helicase superfamily 1/2, ATP-binding domain** (aka N-terminal RecA-like domain) This Interpro ID contains only SF1 and SF2 helicases.
 - [IPR014013](#): **Helicase superfamily 1/2, ATP-binding domain, DinG/Rad3-type**. This identification code is similar to the N-terminal domain (IPR014001), but it differs from other SF1 and SF2 helicases as there is a large insert after the Walker A motif.
 - [IPR041677](#): **DNA2/NAM7 helicase, helicase domain**. DNA2 is a part of the DEAD-like helicase family, which is involved in ATP-dependent RNA or DNA unwinding. Nam7 is an ATP-dependent RNA helicase involved in the nonsense-mediated mRNA decay (NMD) pathway.
 - [IPR001208](#): **MCM domain**. Members of this protein family belong to the AAA+ superfamily. The proteins contain the MCM domain which consists of the Walker A and B, and R-finger motif that are required for ATP hydrolysis. These proteins are required for eukaryotic replication initiation and elongation.
 - [IPR027785](#): **UvrD-like helicase C-terminal Domain**. This C-terminal domain is found in AAA+-like helicases.
 - [IPR014017](#): **UvrD-like DNA helicase, C-terminal**. UvrD-like helicases belong to superfamily 1 helicases. They are unique to classical SF1 and SF2 helicase, as they contain a large insertion in each domain. They are monomeric enzymes, where the RecA-like N-terminal helicase domain is located in the cleft between the N-terminus of the RecA N-terminal helicase domain and the beginning of the RecA-like C-terminal helicase domain.
- There are a total of 95 human helicases (64 RNA and 31 DNA helicases according to a 2011 paper by Pavan Umate et al.). Our database contains 142 probable human helicases that all contain a helicase domain in Uniprot, many of which have helicase-like activities, where they are involved in unwinding nucleotides in an ATP-dependent manner.
 - Two of these human helicases each have 2 pairs of N-terminal and C-terminal helicase domains and are represented twice in the multiple sequence alignment (and the tree) below.
- Similarly, InterPro IDs [IPR001650](#), [IPR006555](#), and [IPR041679](#) were used to compile the list of C-terminal (RecA-like) helicase domains.

- Because of the great diversity of domains and sequences found in helicases, we decided to focus our multiple sequence alignment exclusively on the domains listed above. The N-terminal and, when present, C-terminal sequences were fused with a poly-glycine linker (GGGGG) to generate the final multiple sequence alignment.
- The human protein sequences were aligned using SATe (Liu et al., Science, 2009).
 - Settings:
 - External tools:
 - Aligner - MAFFT
 - Merger - MUSCLE
 - Tree estimator - FASTTREE
 - Model - WAG+G20
 - Sequences and Tree:
 - Data Type - Protein
 - Job Settings:
 - CPU(s) Available - 8
 - Max. Memory (MB) - 1024
 - SATe Settings:
 - Quick Set - SATe-II-fast
 - Max. Subproblem - Size was set to 6
 - Decomposition - Centroid
 - Apply Stop Rule - After Last Improvement
 - Stopping Rule - Blind Model Enabled and Iteration limit was set to 2
 - Return - Best
- Since Interpro and Uniprot are diagnostic tools that predict binding domains, there are times where they miss or incorrectly annotate a sequence of residues as a domain. In these cases, the entire sequence of the protein was used for a pairwise alignment with its closest homolog within our human helicase alignments, found using NCBI BLAST ([NCBI BLAST < Sequence Similarity Searching < EMBL-EBI](#)). Afterwards, only the residues aligned to the human homolog were copied and appended to the final human alignment, using its homolog as a guide in ICM (Molsoft, San Diego).
- Next, viral helicases from the following viral families, all representing a pandemic threat, were added to the alignment: Alphavirus, Norovirus, Enterovirus, Flaviviridae, and Coronaviridae.
- Only the positive sense RNA viruses were included in the alignment. The negative-sense RNA viruses did not have any identified helicase domains or sequences in Uniprot. Positive-sense viral proteins from Goose coronavirus

CB17 and Coronavirus HKU15 were also excluded because they did not have any reviewed N- or C-terminal helicase domain sequences in Uniprot.

- Because the viral sequences had very low homology with human helicases, 3D structural superimpositions were used to guide sequence alignment. One representative viral helicase from each viral family was chosen to be structurally aligned to their closest human helicase match, found with BLAST. The 3D structures of both human and viral helicase were obtained (the structure of Norwalk's helicase was obtained through AlphaFold since it had no crystal structures). The structural alignment was done through a bioinformatic tool called MASS (Dror et al., Bioinformatics, 2003). This tool is an efficient method to derive sequence alignment from structural superimposition.
- The resulting sequence alignment was first replaced using the sequences from Uniprot (because the crystal structure has missing amino acids) and then it was appended to the human helicase alignment.
- Once a representative helicase (ex: SARS-CoV-2 helicase) from a specific viral family (ex: coronavirus) was appended to the multiple sequence alignment, it was used as a guide to append all other helicases (all close homologs) from the same family with high confidence with ICM (Abagyan and Batalov, J. Mol. Biol. 1997)
- ICM (Molsoft, San Diego) was used to create the Newick string of the final alignment, which was then visually represented (Figure 8) with iTol ([iTOL: Interactive Tree Of Life \(embl.de\)](https://itol.embl.de/)).

Results

To construct the multiple sequence alignment for the human helicases, the N-terminal and, when present, the C-terminal helicase domain were obtained using Interpro codes specified in the Methods section of this post. Both helicase domains were linked together through a polyglycine (GGGGG) linker to create the final human helicase core sequence. The following 142 human helicases were then aligned using SATE (SATE settings are listed in the Methods). Before the addition of viral helicases to the alignment, the human multiple sequence alignment was verified for adequacy. Each of the human helicase superfamily were extracted from the multiple sequence alignment using ICM to verify the presence of the family-defining motifs presented above in the introduction. A few (rare) errors in the alignment were detected and mended as per the Methods section. The final resulting alignment of each helicase superfamily is presented below.

Figure 8. The extracted sub-alignment of the SF1 human helicases. The height of the amino acids reflects the level of conservation at a given position, tall letters indicate higher conservation. The sequences between the motifs were removed for simplification. Each coloured box is associated with a SF1 helicase motif. Motif I and II are the Walker A and B motifs, respectively. The colour-coding of boxes highlighting the motifs is conserved in following figures. . For example, the Walker A in each superfamily is shown as a orange-coloured box. Alignment colour-code: yellow: good conservation; green: excellent conservation

Figure 9. The extracted sub-alignment of the first 15 SF2 human helicases. The sequences between the motifs were removed for simplification. The height of the amino acids reflects the level of conservation at a given position, tall letters indicate higher conservation. Each box is associated with a SF2 helicase motif. Colour-code as in Figure 8.

Once the alignment of the human helicases was finalised, viral helicases were added using a structure-based approach. Appending the viral helicases directly to the alignment or aligning the viral and human helicases together resulted in inaccurate alignments due to very low sequence conservation. Instead, a representative viral helicase from each viral family was structurally aligned using MASS to their closest human homolog. The resulting structural alignment was then appended to the multiple sequence alignment using ICM, as outlined in the Methods. Once the model viruses from each family were added to the alignment, the other viral helicases were simply appended to the alignment using the first viral sequence as a guide. The alignment of the viruses were verified to be well aligned to the human helicases since their extracted sub-alignments presented the appropriate motifs, as seen in Figures 10, 11 and 12. The final multiple sequence alignment of both human and viral helicases is attached to this post.

Figure 10. The extracted sub-alignment of the norovirus and enterovirus viral family. They are classified as SF3 helicases as they contain motifs specific for this superfamily. This is not a full alignment, sequences between the motifs have been removed for simplicity. Colour-coding is as in Figure 8.

Figure 11. The extracted sub-alignment of the Flaviviridae viruses. These viral helicases are classified as SF2 helicases. Colour-coding is as in Figure 8.

Figure 12. The extracted sub-alignment of Coronaviridae and Alphavirus from the multiple sequence alignment of both human and viral helicases. These helicases were found to be a part of the SF1 family. Colour-coding is as in Figure 8.

The final multiple sequence alignment was converted into a Newick string and converted into a phylogenetic tree using iTOL (more information can be found in the Methods). Two different phylogenetic trees were constructed to present the superfamilies and families.

Tree scale: 10

- Helicase Superfamilies**
- SF1 Helicase
 - SF2 Helicase
 - SF3 Helicase
 - SF4 Helicase
 - SF6 Helicase
- Species**
- Human
 - Norovirus + Enterovirus
 - Flaviviridae
 - Coronaviridae
 - Alphavirus

Figure 12. A phylogenetic tree representation of the human and viral multiple sequence alignment. The branches on the phylogenetic tree represent the genetic transmission from one generation to the other. The length of the branches indicate genetic change, i.e. the longer the branch, the more divergence or genetic change has occurred. This genetic change is calculated based on residue substitution at each position. The different colours highlighting the helicases represent their superfamily, while the colours surrounding the tree indicate which species or viral family the helicase originates from.

Tree scale: 10

Figure 13. A phylogenetic tree representation of human and viral helicases. This phylogenetic tree is identical to the tree in figure 12. The colours in this figure, however, represent the subfamilies of human helicases and families of viral helicases. Helicase PEO1 (Q96RR1) is labelled as SF4, since it is the only helicase from this superfamily.

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